

EXPLICIT BOUNDS AND PARALLEL ALGORITHMS FOR COUNTING MULTIPLY GLEEFUL NUMBERS

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Abstract

Let $k \geq 1$ be an integer. A positive integer n is *k-gleeful* if n can be represented as the sum of k th powers of consecutive primes. For example, $35 = 2^3 + 3^3$ is a 3-gleeful number, and $195 = 5^2 + 7^2 + 11^2$ is 2-gleeful. First, we extend previous analytical work. For given values of x and k , we give explicit upper and lower bounds on the number of k -gleeful representations of integers $n \leq x$. Second, we describe and analyze two new, efficient parallel algorithms, one theoretical and one practical, to generate all k -gleeful representations up to a bound x . Third, we study integers that are *multiply* gleeful, that is, integers with more than one representation as a sum of powers of consecutive primes, including both the same or different values of k . We give a simple heuristic model for estimating the density of multiply-gleeful numbers, we present empirical data in support of our heuristics, and offer some new conjectures.

1. Introduction

Let $k \geq 1$ be an integer. We say a positive integer n is *k-gleeful* if n can be written as the sum of k th powers of consecutive primes. For example, $35 = 2^3 + 3^3$ is a 3-gleeful number, and $195 = 5^2 + 7^2 + 11^2$ is 2-gleeful. Let $f_k(n)$ denote the number of representations a positive integer n has as a k -gleeful number, and let

$$s_k(x) = \sum_{n=1}^x f_k(n),$$

the total number of k -gleeful representations up to x . In this paper, we address two questions about gleeful numbers and their representations:

- Can we give explicit upper and lower bounds on $s_k(x)$?
- What can we say about integers where $f_k(n) > 1$?

Before we state our results, we give some background on what is already known.

1.1. Previous Work

Moser [9] proved that $s_1(x) \sim x \log 2$. He also posed several interesting questions on the behavior of $f_1(n)$. See also [4]. In this paper, we only look at k -gleeful numbers for integers $k > 1$. Tongsomporn, Wananiyakul, and Steuding [16] proved that

$$s_2(x) < 10.9558 \frac{x^{2/3}}{(\log x)^{4/3}}.$$

They also computed a list of 2-gleeful numbers up to 2000. In [10] it was proved that for every integer $k > 1$,

$$s_k(x) \geq \frac{(k + 1)^2}{2} \cdot \frac{x^{2/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{2k/(k+1)}} \cdot (1 + o(1)) \tag{1}$$

and for $c_k = (k^2/(k - 1))(k + 1)^{1-1/k}$,

$$s_k(x) \leq c_k \cdot \frac{x^{2/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{2k/(k+1)}} (1 + o(1)). \tag{2}$$

Note that $(k + 1)^2 > c_k > (k + 1)^2/2$. They also gave two efficient sequential algorithms: one to enumerate k -gleeful representations and one to compute the exact value of $s_k(x)$, and they presented numerical data supporting their analytical results.

1.2. New Results and Paper Outline

In this paper, we continue the work from [10]. In Section 2, for given values of k and x , we give explicit upper and lower bounds on $s_k(x)$. Our particular interest was to learn more about multiply-gleeful numbers or *duplicates*, that is, integers n with either $f_k(n) > 1$ or both $f_k(n) > 0$ and $f_{k'}(n) > 0$ for $k \neq k'$. We found that the enumeration algorithm from [10] did not work well for finding duplicates, as it requires too much memory. In Section 3, we describe and analyze two parallel algorithms for finding k -gleeful numbers – one practical, the other theoretical. The practical algorithm is based on a sequential routine that finds all k -gleeful numbers in a short interval. The results from that interval are then sorted to detect values

of n with $f_k(n) > 1$. This parallelizes nicely by simply processing short intervals concurrently. To detect duplicates with differing k values, the algorithm is run twice on the same interval, once for each k value, and again, the interval's results are sorted to detect the duplicates. Our theoretical algorithm shows this problem is in \mathcal{NC} [3]. Then, in Section 4, we describe a heuristic model that predicts how many duplicates we expect to find up to x . We evaluated our model using data generated by our new parallel algorithm. We state some conjectures consistent with these results. See [15] for our code and data.

2. Explicit Bounds

In this section, we prove the following theorems, which are explicit versions of Theorem 1 from [10].

Let p_n denote the n th prime with $p_1 = 2$. The number of primes up to x is given by $\pi(x)$. For fixed x and $k \geq 2$ an integer, let $M := M(x, k)$ be the maximum length of any representation of any integer up to x , so that

$$2^k + 3^k + \dots + p_M^k \leq x < 2^k + 3^k + \dots + p_M^k + p_{M+1}^k. \tag{3}$$

Observe that for a given k , any bound on M implies a bound on x . Let M_0 be a fixed integer, at least 6. Our results depend on $M(x, k)$ being larger than M_0 . Choosing M_0 to be larger gives better explicit constants.

We define the following functions on y and k . We will be plugging M_0 in for y :

$$\begin{aligned} c_k &= \left(\frac{k^2}{k-1}\right) \cdot (k+1)^{(k-1)/k} \quad \text{from Equation (2),} \\ A(y) &:= \frac{\log(y/2)}{\log y}, \\ B(y, k) &:= \frac{\log(y+1)}{\log y} + \frac{\log \log(y+1)^2}{\log y} \frac{k}{k+1}, \\ C(y, k) &:= \left(\frac{y}{y-1}\right)^{1/(k+1)} B(y, k)^{k/(k+1)}, \\ D(y, k) &:= \left(\frac{y}{y+3}\right) \left(\frac{\log(y/2)}{\log y + 2 \log \log(y+2)}\right)^{k/(k+1)}, \\ E(y, k) &:= 1 + \frac{1}{(k+1)A(y) - 1}, \\ F(y, k) &:= \left(\frac{y+1}{y}\right)^{(k-1)/k} \cdot 4^{(k-1)/(k(k+1))} \cdot C(y, k)^{(k-1)/k} \cdot E(y, k), \\ U(y, k) &:= 1.25506 \cdot F(y, k), \end{aligned}$$

$$L(y, k) := \left(\frac{y-1}{y}\right) \cdot D(y, k)^2.$$

Note that $A(y), B(y, k), C(y, k), D(y, k) \rightarrow 1$ for large y , and $E(y, k) \rightarrow 1 + 1/k$ for large y .

Theorem 1. *For $k > 1$ and $M \geq M_0 \geq 6$, we have*

$$s_k(x) \leq c_k \cdot \frac{x^{2/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{k/(k+1)}} \cdot U(M_0, k).$$

For $k = 2$, in [16] they give a constant of 10.9558. Here, for $k = 2$, we get the weaker 14.2423 for $M \geq M_0 = 6$. The results in [10] give a constant of $c_2 = 4 \cdot \sqrt{3} \approx 6.928$, for large x .

Theorem 2. *For $k > 1$ and $M \geq M_0 \geq 6$, we have*

$$s_k(x) \geq \frac{(k+1)^2}{2} \cdot \frac{x^{2/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{k/(k+1)}} \cdot L(M_0, k).$$

In Table 1 we illustrate Theorems 1 and 2; we show two numbers for each combination of M_0 and k : the lower bound constant, $\frac{(k+1)^2}{2} \cdot L(M_0, k)$, followed by the upper bound constant, $c_k \cdot U(M_0, k)$.

$M_0 =$	6	100	10000	1000000
$k = 2$	0.391, 14.3	1.71, 12.2	2.39, 11.7	2.73, 11.6
$k = 3$	0.580, 23.5	2.72, 18.8	3.93, 17.8	4.56, 17.4
$k = 5$	1.09, 63.2	5.47, 48.1	8.19, 44.5	9.65, 42.9
$k = 10$	3.10, 250	16.6, 183	25.6, 165	30.6, 158
$k = 20$	10.3, 1010	57.0, 721	89.7, 643	108, 610

Table 1: Constants for lower and upper bounds on $s_k(x)$

2.1. Setup

Let us define $f_{k,m}(n)$ to be the number of representations of n as a sum of exactly m k th powers of consecutive primes. Observe that $f_{k,m}(n) = 0$ or 1 and that

$$f_k(n) = \sum_{m=1}^M f_{k,m}(n).$$

Let $s_{k,m}(x)$ be the number of positive integers n such that

$$p_n^k + p_{n+1}^k + \dots + p_{n+m-1}^k \leq x.$$

Then

$$s_{k,m}(x) = \sum_{n=1}^x f_{k,m}(n)$$

so that

$$s_k(x) = \sum_{n=1}^x f_k(n) = \sum_{n=1}^x \sum_{m=1}^M f_{k,m}(n) = \sum_{m=1}^M s_{k,m}(x).$$

This counts the number of representations of k -gleeful numbers up to x .

We will make use of the following results due to Rosser and Schonfeld [13] and Rosser [12]:

$$n \log n < p_n \quad \text{for } n \geq 1, \tag{4}$$

$$p_n < n \log n + 2n \log \log n \quad \text{for } n \geq 3, \tag{5}$$

$$p_n < 2n \log n \quad \text{for } n \geq 3, \text{ and} \tag{6}$$

$$\pi(x) < 1.25506 \frac{x}{\log x} \quad \text{for } x \geq 2. \tag{7}$$

2.2. Proof of Theorem 1

We begin with the following two lemmas, which provide us with upper and lower bounds on M .

Lemma 1. *Let $k > 1$ be an integer. If $M \geq M_0 \geq 6$ then*

$$M < 4^{1/(k+1)} \cdot \frac{(k+1)x^{1/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{k/(k+1)}} \cdot C(M_0, k).$$

Lemma 2. *Let $k > 1$ be an integer. If $M \geq M_0 \geq 6$ then*

$$M \geq (k+1) \cdot \frac{x^{1/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{k/(k+1)}} \cdot D(M_0, k).$$

For large M , from [10] we expect $M \sim (k+1) \cdot x^{1/(k+1)} / (\log x)^{k/(k+1)}$. See Table 2 for some exact values of $M(x, k)$.

As stepping stones, the proofs of these two lemmas utilize easier-to-prove upper and lower bounds on $\log M$ in terms of x and k .

Lemma 3. *Let $k > 1$ be an integer. If $M \geq M_0 \geq 6$ then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \log M &< \frac{\log x}{k+1} \cdot \frac{1}{A(M_0)} \quad \text{and} \\ \log M &\geq \frac{\log x}{k+1} \cdot \frac{1}{B(M_0, k)}. \end{aligned}$$

As we let M_0 get larger, we get the expected $(k+1) \log M \sim \log x$.

x	$M(x, 2)$	$M(x, 3)$	$M(x, 5)$	$M(x, 10)$	$M(x, 20)$
10^3	7	4	2	0	0
10^4	14	7	3	1	0
10^5	28	11	4	2	0
10^6	54	18	6	2	0
10^7	105	29	8	3	1
10^8	207	47	11	3	1
10^9	411	77	15	4	1
10^{10}	822	126	21	4	2
10^{11}	1656	209	30	5	2
10^{12}	3356	348	40	6	2
10^{13}	6834	581	55	8	2
10^{14}	13975	974	76	9	3
10^{15}	28682	1640	106	10	3
10^{16}	59066	2771	148	12	3
10^{17}	121987	4695	206	15	4
10^{18}	252574	7977	288	17	4
10^{19}	524136	13589	403	20	4
10^{20}	1089888	23201	566	24	4

Table 2: Exact values of $M(x, k)$ for various x, k

Proof. Since $M \geq 6$, we can bound the sum on the left of (3) from below by $(M/2)p_{M/2}^k$. Taking $(M/2)\log(M/2) < p_{M/2}$ from (4), we have

$$(M/2)^{k+1}(\log(M/2))^k < x.$$

Because $M \geq 6 > 2e$, we can drop the $(\log(M/2))^k$ term since it exceeds 1. Taking logarithms of both sides then gives

$$\begin{aligned} \log x > (k + 1)\log(M/2) &= (k + 1)(\log M) \left(1 - \frac{\log 2}{\log M}\right) \\ &\geq (k + 1)(\log M) \left(1 - \frac{\log 2}{\log M_0}\right). \end{aligned}$$

The sum on the right of (3) is bounded above by $(M + 1)p_{M+1}^k$. Using (6) gives

$$\log x < (k + 1)\log(M + 1) + k\log(2\log(M + 1)).$$

With $M \geq M_0$, we know that

$$\log(M + 1) = \frac{\log(M + 1)}{\log M} \log M < \frac{\log(M_0 + 1)}{\log M_0} \log M. \tag{8}$$

We also know that when $M \geq M_0 \geq 6$,

$$\frac{\log(2\log(M + 1))}{\log(M + 1)}$$

is maximized when $M = M_0$. This then gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\log x}{k+1} &\leq (\log M) \left(1 + \frac{\log \log(M_0 + 1)^2}{\log(M_0 + 1)} \frac{k}{k+1} \right) \frac{\log(M_0 + 1)}{\log M_0} \\ &= (\log M) \left(\frac{\log(M_0 + 1)}{\log M_0} + \frac{\log \log(M_0 + 1)^2}{\log M_0} \frac{k}{k+1} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Plugging in the definitions of $A(M_0), B(M_0, k)$ completes the proof. □

Proof of Lemma 1. Next, we bound x from below in terms of M and k . Using (3) and (4), We have

$$\begin{aligned} x &\geq p_1^k + p_2^k + \dots + p_M^k \\ &> \sum_{n=1}^M (n \log n)^k \geq \sum_{n=M^{1-1/k}}^M (n \log n)^k \\ &\geq (\log M^{1-1/k})^k \sum_{n=M^{1-1/k}}^M n^k \\ &= (1 - 1/k)^k (\log M)^k \sum_{n=M^{1-1/k}}^M n^k. \end{aligned}$$

We can bound the sum on n^k with an integral to get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=M^{1-1/k}}^M n^k &\geq \int_{M^{1-1/k}}^M t^k dt = \frac{M^{k+1} - M^{(k+1)(1-1/k)}}{k+1} \\ &= \frac{M^{k+1} - M^{k-1/k}}{k+1} = \frac{M^{k+1}}{k+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{M^{1+1/k}} \right) \\ &> \frac{M^{k+1}}{k+1} \cdot \frac{M_0 - 1}{M_0} \end{aligned}$$

if $M \geq M_0$. We also have $(1 - 1/k)^k \geq 1/4$ for $k \geq 2$. Pulling this together gives

$$x \geq \frac{M^{k+1} (\log M)^k}{4(k+1)} \cdot \frac{M_0 - 1}{M_0},$$

which is valid when $M \geq M_0$. This directly gives

$$M^{k+1} \leq \frac{4(k+1)x}{(\log M)^k} \cdot \frac{M_0}{M_0 - 1}.$$

Applying Lemma 3 then gives

$$M^{k+1} < \frac{4 \cdot (k+1)^{k+1} x}{(\log x)^k} \cdot \frac{M_0}{M_0 - 1} B(M_0, k)^k$$

and

$$M < 4^{1/(k+1)} \frac{(k+1)x^{1/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{k/(k+1)}} \cdot \left(\frac{M_0}{M_0-1}\right)^{1/(k+1)} B(M_0, k)^{k/(k+1)}.$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 1. □

Proof of Lemma 2. Again, starting from (3), observing that $2^k + 3^k < 5^k < p_{M+2}^k$, and applying (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} x &\leq p_1^k + \dots + p_{M+1}^k \leq p_3^k + \dots + p_{M+2}^k \\ &\leq \sum_{n=3}^{M+2} n^k (\log n + 2 \log \log n)^k \\ &\leq (\log(M+2) + 2 \log \log(M+2))^k \sum_{n=3}^{M+2} n^k \\ &\leq (\log(M+2) + 2 \log \log(M+2))^k \frac{(M+3)^{k+1}}{k+1} \\ &\leq (\log M)^k \left(\frac{\log(M_0+2)}{\log M_0} + \frac{2 \log \log(M_0+2)}{\log M_0} \right)^k \frac{(M+3)^{k+1}}{k+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Here we bounded the sum $\sum_{n=3}^{M+2} n^k$ with an integral to get $\frac{(M+3)^{k+1}}{k+1}$. Using (8), we have

$$x \leq (\log M)^k \frac{((M_0+3)/M_0) \cdot M^{k+1}}{k+1} \left(\frac{\log(M_0+2)}{\log M_0} + \frac{2 \log \log(M_0+2)}{\log M_0} \right)^k,$$

or

$$(k+1) \frac{x}{(\log M)^k} \frac{(M_0/(M_0+3))^{k+1}}{\left(\frac{\log(M_0+2)}{\log M_0} + \frac{2 \log \log(M_0+2)}{\log M_0}\right)^k} \leq M^{k+1}.$$

We apply Lemma 3 and simplify a bit to obtain

$$\frac{(k+1)x^{1/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{k/(k+1)}} \cdot \left(\frac{M_0}{M_0+3}\right) \left(\frac{\log(M_0/2)}{\log(M_0+2) + 2 \log \log(M_0+2)}\right)^{k/(k+1)} \leq M.$$

This completes the proof. □

We are now ready to prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. For positive integers n, m , we refer to any sum of the form $p_n^k + p_{n+1}^k + \dots + p_{n-1+m}^k$ as a *chain* of length m . Recall that

$$s_{k,m}(x) = \#\{n : p_n^k + p_{n+1}^k + \dots + p_{n-1+m}^k \leq x\},$$

the number of k -gleeful representations of integers less than or equal to x of length m , or the number of chains of length m whose sums are bounded by x .

For the moment, fix a chain length m . Choose n , the starting point of the chain, as large as possible so that we have

$$m \cdot p_n^k \leq p_n^k + p_{n+1}^k + \cdots + p_{n-1+m}^k \leq x \leq p_{n+1}^k + p_{n+2}^k + \cdots + p_{n+m}^k.$$

This gives

$$\begin{aligned} mp_n^k &\leq x, \\ p_n &\leq (x/m)^{1/k}, \\ n &\leq \pi((x/m)^{1/k}). \end{aligned}$$

Observe that $s_{k,m}(x) = n$ here. (See Lemma 1 from [10].) Thus,

$$s_k(x) = \sum_{m=1}^M s_{k,m}(x) \leq \sum_{m=1}^M \pi((x/m)^{1/k}).$$

Observe that $(x/m)^{1/k} \geq (p_M^k/M)^{1/k} > 2$ for $M \geq 6$. From (7) we have

$$\pi(t) \leq 1.25506 \cdot t / \log t$$

when $t \geq 2$. This gives

$$\begin{aligned} s_k(x) &\leq \sum_{m=1}^M \pi((x/m)^{1/k}) \\ &\leq 1.25506 \cdot \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{k(x/m)^{1/k}}{\log(x/m)} \\ &\leq 1.25506 \cdot \frac{kx^{1/k}}{\log(x/M)} \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{1}{m^{1/k}}. \end{aligned}$$

Focusing first on the logarithm in the denominator, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \log(x/M) &\geq \log x - \frac{\log x}{(k+1)A(M_0)} \quad \text{or} \\ \frac{1}{\log(x/M)} &\leq \frac{1}{\log x} \left(1 + \frac{1}{(k+1)A(M_0) - 1} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\log x} \cdot E(M_0, k) \end{aligned}$$

using Lemma 3. Next, we estimate the sum:

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{1}{m^{1/k}} \leq \int_1^{M+1} t^{-1/k} dt$$

$$\leq \frac{(M + 1)^{1-1/k}}{1 - 1/k}.$$

Pulling this together, we have

$$\begin{aligned} s_k(x) &\leq 1.25506 \cdot E(M_0, k) \cdot \frac{kx^{1/k} (M + 1)^{1-1/k}}{\log x (1 - 1/k)} \\ &\leq 1.25506 \cdot E(M_0, k) \cdot \left(\frac{M_0 + 1}{M_0}\right)^{(k-1)/k} \left(\frac{k^2}{k-1}\right) \frac{x^{1/k}}{\log x} \cdot M^{(k-1)/k}, \end{aligned}$$

since $M \geq M_0$. Next, we plug in our upper bound on M from Lemma 1. We have

$$M^{(k-1)/k} < 4^{(k-1)/(k(k+1))} \cdot (k + 1)^{(k-1)/k} \cdot C(M_0, k)^{(k-1)/k} \cdot \frac{x^{(k-1)/(k(k+1))}}{(\log x)^{(k-1)/(k+1)}}.$$

Plugging this in, we obtain

$$s_k(x) \leq 1.25506 \cdot c_k \cdot \frac{x^{2/(k+1)}}{(\log x)^{2k/(k+1)}} \cdot F(M_0, y),$$

and the result follows. □

2.3. Proof of Theorem 2

Proof. Any subsequence sum of the maximum chain length M represents a k -gleeful number up to x . Thus, the number of i, j pairs such that $1 \leq i \leq j \leq M$, or $\binom{M}{2}$, is a lower bound for $s_k(x)$. Thus,

$$s_k(x) \geq \binom{M}{2} = \frac{M(M - 1)}{2} \geq \frac{M_0 - 1}{2M_0} \cdot M^2$$

since we are assuming $M \geq M_0$. Simply apply Lemma 2 and a bit of algebra and the result follows. □

3. Two Parallel Algorithms

We begin with a straightforward adaptation of the enumeration algorithm from [10] to work on an interval.

3.1. An Algorithm to Enumerate Representations on an Interval

Here we describe an algorithm that generates all integers n with $f_k(n) > 0$, where $x_1 \leq n < x_2$ for inputs k, x_1, x_2 . We obtain the original algorithm from [10] by setting $(x_1, x_2) = (1, x)$.

Let x be the largest value of x_2 we plan to use in any application of this algorithm. As a preprocessing step, we find all primes up to $x^{1/k}$ and compute the prefix array $r[\]$, where $r[0] = 0$ and $r[j] = r[j - 1] + p_j^k$ where p_j is the j th prime with $p_1 = 2$.

For a particular value of n with $f_k(n) > 0$, we write $n = r[t] - r[b]$, a difference of prefix sum values, which gives its representation as $p_{b+1}^k + \dots + p_t^k$. The trick is to generate exactly the correct values of b and t to ensure that $x_1 \leq n < x_2$. The outer loop iterates through all possible b values, and the inner loop iterates through the correct t values. Let t_s indicate the smallest t for a given b . Observe that as b increases, t_s is non-decreasing and $t_s > b$. See Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Enumerate integers n with $x_1 \leq n < x_2$ and $f_k(n) > 0$

Require: Integers $k > 1$, $x_1 < x_2$, a list of all primes up to $x_2^{1/k}$, and the prefix sum array $r[\]$

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 $t_s \leftarrow 1$ 
 $\ell \leftarrow \pi(x_2^{1/k})$ 
for  $b \leftarrow 0$  to  $\ell$  do
    while  $t_s \leq \ell$  and  $t_s \leq b$  do
         $t_s \leftarrow t_s + 1$ 
    end while
    while  $t_s \leq \ell$  and  $r[t_s] - r[b] < x_1$  do
         $t_s \leftarrow t_s + 1$ 
    end while
    for  $t \leftarrow t_s$  to  $\ell$  do
         $n \leftarrow r[t] - r[b]$ 
        if  $x_1 \leq n < x_2$  then
            output  $(n, p_{b+1})$ 
        else if  $n \geq x_2$  then
            break the inner for loop (on  $t$ )
        end if
    end for
end for

```

The running time of this algorithm is bounded by a constant times the number of times through the while loops and the inner for loop. Observe that the while loops increment t_s , which is bounded by $\ell = \pi(x_2^{1/k})$, so the total number of while loop iterations is bounded by ℓ . The number of times we iterate through the inner for loop is bounded by a constant times the number of times the output (n, p_{b+1}) statement executes, which in turn is $s_k(x_2) - s_k(x_1)$.

We have proven the following theorem.

Theorem 3. *Given integers $k > 1$ and $x_1 < x_2 \leq x$, Algorithm 1 will list all integers n with $f_k(n) > 0$ and $x_1 \leq n < x_2$. The number of arithmetic operations used by the algorithm is at most $O(x^{1/k} / \log \log x + (s_k(x_2) - s_k(x_1)))$.*

In addition, for every representation of n as a k -gleeful number, the first prime in that representation is also given.

We have a few comments:

- The understanding is that x is an upper bound on the application of the algorithm, and that it may be used on multiple intervals $[x_1, x_2)$ with $x_1 < x_2 \leq x$. We are also assuming here that k is fixed, but x (and x_1, x_2) are large.
- The $x^{1/k} / \log \log x$ term is the time to compute the list of primes up to $x^{1/k}$ using, say, the Atkin-Bernstein algorithm [2]. If the primes are already available, this term changes to $\pi(x_2^{1/k}) - \pi(x_1^{1/k}) = O(kx^{1/k} / \log x)$.
- In practice, we make the interval length $x_2 - x_1$ large enough so that we expect $s_k(x_2) - s_k(x_1) \gg x^{1/k}$, thereby ensuring that the cost of managing the list of primes becomes negligible.
- We obtain a practical parallel algorithm by dividing the range $(1, x)$ into equal-sized intervals of length $\Delta = x_2 - x_1$. We then assign one processor to each interval. Thus, x/Δ processors can run in parallel using minimal communication overhead, and the list of primes and the prefix sum array $r[]$ can be shared.
- When searching for duplicates, which are integers n with either $f_k(n) > 1$ or both $f_k(n) > 0$ and $f_{k'}(n) > 0$ for $k \neq k'$, the interval of size Δ should be sorted to look for matches. Note that a list of integers in a limited range can be sorted in linear time using a radix or bucket-style sort.

In practice, we found that Quicksort [5] was good enough. See [6, Section 5.2.5].

3.2. A Theoretical Parallel Algorithm

We describe the steps and analyze the algorithm as we go. We assume an EREW PRAM parallel model with arithmetic operations on integers with $O(\log x)$ bits taking constant time. Note that $\pi(x^{1/k}) = O(kx^{1/k} / \log x)$ by the prime number theorem. As above, we use ℓ for the number of such primes.

1. To find the primes up to $x^{1/k}$, we use the algorithm from [14]. This takes $O((1/k) \log x)$ time and $O(kx^{1/k} / (\log x \log \log x))$ processors.
2. To compute the k th powers of all the primes, we use a sequential binary exponentiation algorithm that takes $O(\log k) = O(\log \log x)$ time, since we can assume $k = O(\log x)$ here. We apply this to all primes in parallel, taking $\ell = O(kx^{1/k} / \log x)$ processors.

3. The prefix sum array $r[]$ can be computed in $O(\log \ell)$ time using $O(\ell/\log \ell)$ processors, or $O((1/k) \log x)$ time and $O(k^2 x^{1/k}/(\log x)^2)$ processors.
4. To start, we assign one processor to each b value from 0 to ℓ . Then, for each b in parallel, we perform a binary search on the $r[]$ array to find the correct start and stop t values, $(t_1(b), t_2(b))$ so that for every t with $t_1(b) \leq t \leq t_2(b)$, we have $0 < r[t] - r[b] < x$. This takes $O(\log \ell)$ time using $O(\ell)$ processors since this is how many b values there are.
5. For each b , we allocate $(t_2(b) - t_1(b))/\log \ell$ additional processors. This is a total of $O(\ell + s_k(x)/\log \ell)$ processors overall.
6. For every b , in parallel we compute $n = r[t] - r[b]$ for every $t_1(b) \leq t \leq t_2(b)$ and output (p_{b+1}, n) . This uses the processors allocated in the previous step. Each processor may have to do up to $O(\log \ell)$ such computations, but they take constant time each. This takes $O(\log \ell)$ time using $O(\ell + s_k(x)/\log \ell)$ processors.

We have proven the following.

Theorem 4. *There is an EREW PRAM algorithm to find all integers $n \leq x$ with $f_k(n) > 0$ that uses at most $O(\log \ell)$ time and $O(\ell + s_k(x)/\log \ell)$ processors, where $\ell := \pi(x^{1/k}) = O(kx^{1/k}/\log x)$.*

Note that this algorithm is work-optimal, and proves that computing $s_k(x)$ is in the complexity class \mathcal{NC} .

4. Duplicates

In this section, we examine, heuristically, the distribution of duplicates, which come in two varieties:

1. Integers n with $f_k(n) > 1$, or
2. Integers n with both $f_k(n) > 0$ and $f_{k'}(n) > 0$ for $k \neq k'$.

Without loss of generality, in the second type we shall henceforth assume $k < k'$.

In the spirit of Cramér’s model, we assume that an integer $n \leq x$ is k -gleeful with probability given by

$$s_k(x)/x. \tag{9}$$

4.1. Duplicates for $f_k(n) > 1$

Assuming (9), a first try at estimating the probability an integer $n \leq x$ is a duplicate with $f_k(n) > 1$ would be simply

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{s_k(x)}{x}\right)^2 &\approx \frac{k^4 x^{4/(k+1)}}{x^2 (\log x)^{2k/(k+1)}} \\ &= x^{4/(k+1)-2} \cdot \frac{k^4}{(\log x)^{2k/(k+1)}}. \end{aligned}$$

This probability is $o(1/x)$, unless $k < 3$. When $k = 2$ we might expect the density of duplicates to be around $x^{1/3}/(\log x)^{4/3}$, which implies there are infinitely many examples.

A potential flaw in our logic is that two different gleeful representations for n with the same value of k must be of different lengths. Recall that

$$s_k(x) = \sum_{m=1}^{M(x,k)} s_{k,m}(x).$$

Thus, a finer estimate for the probability of a duplicate is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{x^2} \sum_{m_1=1}^{M(x,k)} s_{m_1,k}(x) \sum_{m_2 < m_1} s_{m_2,k}(x) \\ &= \frac{1}{x^2} \sum_{m_1=1}^{M(x,k)} \sum_{m_2 < m_1} s_{m_1,k}(x) s_{m_2,k}(x) \\ &\approx \frac{1}{x^2} \sum_{m_1=1}^{M(x,k)} \sum_{m_2 < m_1} \pi((x/m_1)^{1/k}) \cdot \pi((x/m_2)^{1/k}). \end{aligned}$$

By the prime number theorem, this is asymptotic to

$$\begin{aligned} &\sim \frac{1}{x^2} \sum_{m_1=1}^{M(x,k)} \sum_{m_2 < m_1} \frac{k^2 x^{2/k}}{(m_1 m_2)^{1/k} \log(x^2/(m_1 m_2))} \\ &\approx \frac{k^2 x^{2/k-2}}{2 \log(x/M)} \sum_{m_1=1}^{M(x,k)} m_1^{-1/k} \sum_{m_2 < m_1} m_2^{-1/k} \\ &\approx \frac{k^2 x^{2/k-2}}{2 \log(x/M)} \sum_{m_1=1}^{M(x,k)} m_1^{-1/k} \cdot \frac{m_1^{1-1/k}}{1-1/k} \\ &\approx \frac{k^3 x^{2/k-2}}{2(k-1) \log(x/M)} \sum_{m_1=1}^{M(x,k)} m_1^{1-2/k}. \end{aligned}$$

If $k = 2$, the sum is just $M(x, 2) \sim 3x^{1/3}/(\log x)^{2/3}$, which gives a probability of

$$\frac{4M}{x \log(x/M)} \sim \frac{18}{x^{2/3}(\log x)^{5/3}},$$

smaller than our first estimate by a factor of roughly $(\log x)^{1/3}$, but still enough that we expect infinitely many integers n with $f_2(n) > 1$.

If $k \geq 3$, we end up with the following probability:

$$\frac{k^3 x^{2/k}}{2(k-1)x^2 \log(x/M)} \cdot \frac{M^{2-2/k}}{2-2/k}.$$

Plugging in our estimate that $M \approx (k+1)x^{1/(k+1)}/(\log x)^{k/(k+1)}$, we obtain the probability

$$\frac{k^3(k+1)}{2(k-1)} \cdot \frac{x^{4/(k+1)-2}}{(\log x)^{(3k-1)/(k+1)}}.$$

For $k > 3$ this is clearly $o(1/x)$, as the exponent on x is less than -1 . For $k = 3$ the exponent on x is exactly -1 , but the log factor in the denominator still gives us $o(1/x)$.

This leads us to the following conjectures.

Conjecture 1. There are infinitely many integers n with $f_2(n) > 1$.

We found 1950 integers $n \leq 10^{18}$ with $f_2(n) > 1$. Let us set

$$d(x) := x^{1/3}/(\log x)^{5/3},$$

the number of integers n below x we expect to find with $f_2(n) > 1$, with the constant factor 18 dropped. As we can see in Figure 1, $d(x)$ lines up very nicely with our data. We currently have no explanation for why our prediction above is off by a factor of 18.

Conjecture 2. For each integer $k \geq 3$, there are finitely many integers n with $f_k(n) > 1$.

With a bit more work, our heuristics also lead to this much stronger conjecture.

Conjecture 3. There are finitely many integers n with $f_k(n) > 1$ for *any* $k \geq 3$.

We have not found any examples n with $f_k(n) > 1, k > 2$. Our code and data are available at [15].

4.2. Duplicates for $f_k(n) > 0$ and $f_{k'}(n) > 0$ with $k < k'$

We continue to assume $k < k'$. The heuristic probability that a randomly chosen integer $n \leq x$ has both $f_k(n), f_{k'}(n) > 0$ is at most

$$\frac{s_k(x)s_{k'}(x)}{x^2} \approx (kk')^2 \frac{x^{2/(k+1)+2/(k'+1)-2}}{(\log x)^{2k/(k+1)+2k'/(k'+1)}}.$$

Figure 1: Comparing $d(x)$ to the number of $n \leq x$ with $f_2(n) > 1$.

With the log factors in the denominator, we can expect infinitely many examples if the exponent on x is strictly greater than -1 , that is, $2/(k+1) + 2/(k'+1) - 2 > -1$, or

$$\frac{2}{k+1} + \frac{2}{k'+1} > 1.$$

With $k' > k$, this is not true when $k \geq 3$. With $k = 2$, we then require $2/(k'+1) > 1/3$. This gives $k' = 3$ or 4 .

Conjecture 4. For $k' = 3$ or 4 , there are infinitely many integers n with both $f_2(n) > 0$ and $f_{k'}(n) > 0$.

We have 3 examples of 2-3 duplicates up to 10^{18} :

$$23939, \quad 432958700126053, \quad 137610738498311684.$$

We found no 2-4 duplicates below 10^{18} . We are hopeful that more examples will eventually be found.

Conjecture 5. For $k < k'$, if $k \geq 3$ or $k' \geq 5$ then there are finitely many integers n with both $f_k(n) > 0$ and $f_{k'}(n) > 0$.

Recently, Florian Luca has shown that there are infinitely many n such that $f_2(n)f_4(n) > 0$, and that $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_2(n) \rightarrow \infty$, both under the assumption of Schinzel's Hypothesis H [7, 8].

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